

Eine Level-Set Methode zur Simulation von Schmelzvorgängen

A Level-Set Method for the Simulation of Melting

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Glossary

Greek Symbols

α	thermal diffusivity
κ	thermal conductivity
ν	kinematic viscosity
Γ	spatial boundary (domain description), a curve or embedded hyperplane (interface description)
Ω	spatial domain
η	dynamic viscosity, (in the context of finite elements:) set of nodes
ρ	density
λ	similarity parameter (in the analytical solution of the single-phase Stefan problem)

Roman Symbols

C	a crossing or cut of the PCI with a (FEM) mesh face
c_p	specific heat capacity
h_m	latent heat (of melting)
n_Ω	number of (FEM) mesh nodes
n_{PCI}	number of crossings of the PCI with element faces
n_t	number of time steps
p	pressure
q	heat flux
\dot{Q}	heat flow rate
t	continuous time or discrete time instance
T	temperature
U	melting velocity

u	velocity (of the flow field)
v	level-set advection velocity

Indices

B	boundary
C	surface of the ice (see also PCI)
eq	at an equilibrium condition (in the ice)
H	heating surface
h	numerical (FEM) solution
L	liquid phase
M	melting point
n	at the n^{th} time step t^n
PCI	on the phase-change interface
S	solid phase
s	far field of the solid phase

Acronyms

CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CFL	Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (Condition)
EOC	Experimental Order of Convergence
FEM	Finite-Element Method
INS	Incompressible Navier-Stokes (Equations)
PCI	Phase-Change Interface
XFEM	Extended Finite-Element Methods
XNS	a CFD Solver written in Fortran[1]

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1. Introduction

In our daily lives we are constantly surrounded by the interaction of different phases of the most diverse materials. We observe phenomena exhibiting phase transitions in a broad field of applications ranging from cooking to space science and the development of accurate and fast numerical tools for multi-phase simulations remains an active topic of research. Fig. 1 shows some examples of processes, in which phase transitions of one or more materials are of importance.

(a) Eyjafjallajökull glacier [2]

(b) Molten metal at a furnace outlet [3]

(c) Noodles in boiling water [4]

(d) Welding of metal parts [5]

Figure 1: Examples of different phenomena involving multiple material phases.

In this project paper we will briefly review some of the most important numerical methods for multi-phase simulations. Special emphasis is put on the *level-set method*, which is popular among researchers from different application backgrounds [6]. While many authors employ finite-difference schemes for the discretization of the governing equations and the level-set equation [7], [8], [9], [10], successful attempts using finite elements have been made [11], [12]. Finite element methods (FEM) profit from their increased versatility in terms of the geometry of the discretized domain and their widespread use throughout all engineering applications. Standard Galerkin FEM do however fail to accurately capture discontinuous derivatives across the interface be-

tween phases, which are crucial to impose the correct interface boundary condition. A remedy is to employ local enrichment of the [FEM](#) basis on nodes close to the interface.

In this project paper we present a solution algorithm for Stefan-type melting problems using the level-set and finite element methods ([FEM](#)). We describe a strategy for approximate computation of the melting velocity at the interface based on the idea of *ghost cells* [8], which is applicable to general choices of (non-enriched) [FEM](#) basis functions and arbitrary mesh geometries. The algorithm is validated against the analytical solution of the 1D single-phase Stefan problem and then tested on 2D structured and unstructured meshes. We also demonstrate the full coupling between flow and temperature solution in a melting scenario.

The simulation will be performed using *space-time FEM*, implemented in the [XNS](#) framework [1]. The software is developed at the Chair of Computational Analysis of Technical Systems of the RWTH Aachen University.

For better accessibility we start by presenting the basic framework of two-phase problems in Chapter 2. The governing equations as well as the level-set method are introduced herein on a conceptual level. We also give a very brief review of finite element methods and we explain why it is difficult to recover good approximations of the melting velocity with standard formulations.

In Chapter 3 we leverage on existing work by Gibou and Fedkiw [8], [13], [9] on the *ghost cell* approach, to describe an extension of the ghost split to arbitrary [FEM](#) meshes. This method circumvents the need for an adaptive enrichment of the [FEM](#) basis. Here we also discuss the approximation of the melting velocity using nodal temperature gradients.

We apply the described algorithm to several numerical test cases in Chapter 4, where we start with a 1D validation of the algorithm against the analytical solution of the single-phase Stefan problem. Convergence in the numerical prediction of the interface location is presented under spatial refinement. We then show a coupled simulation of temperature and flow for a lid-driven melting test case. Finally, the applicability to unstructured meshes is tested with a heated cylinder test case.

In Chapter 5 we summarize our findings, giving suggestions for improvements and necessary future work.

2. Two-Phase Problems

Before we provide a more in-depth description of the system of governing equations and numerical methods, we will give a short conceptual overview over the two-phase problem at hand. This overview shall outline the big picture of our solution strategy and serve as an orientation for the reader, to contextualize the algorithm steps described in later sections.

While in general multi-phase problems may refer to problems containing arbitrary miscible or immiscible species, we will confine ourselves to the description of a binary composition of phases. More specifically we will consider the liquid and solid phase of a single species (e.g. water), but the general concept of the numerical methods proposed in this project paper can be applied to other types of phase transitions with only slight modifications. Fig. 2 shows a sketch of a general two-phase problem. Two different phases denoted by the subscript $i \in \{1, 2\}$ exhibit different material properties, e.g. different densities ρ_i , viscosities μ_i and thermal conductivities k_i and are separated by the *phase change interface* (PCI). While material properties can and will generally be inhomogeneous and obey different phase-specific material laws, we will assume them to be uniform across a phase within the scope of this project paper. Note however, that the numerical methods proposed hereinafter are not limited to the case of phase-wise constant properties.

In this project we will propose a solution strategy for 2D melting and solidification problems based on a level-set formulation for space-time finite elements. The physical description of the two-phase problem is based on the following primal unknowns:

- the pressure $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$,
- the velocity field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (u, v, w)^T$,
- and the temperature field $T(\mathbf{x}, t)$

We will consider the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations (INS) and the unsteady energy equation formulated in terms of the temperature T in the domain. These governing equations are detailed in Section 2.1.

One major difficulty is the accurate prediction of the phase at time instance t and at each location \mathbf{x} in the spatial domain Ω (see Fig. 2b). This information is essential for the numerical solution of the governing equations since again we associate different material properties with each phase. Fig. 3 is meant to give a compact review of the essential building blocks described in this project paper as well as the basic flow of information between them. The bold capital letters used in the next paragraphs refer to the blocks in Fig. 3.

(a) General Two-Phase Problem

(b) Mathematical Domain

Figure 2: Concept sketch of a two-phase problem. On the left a general domain comprising two phases ($i \in \{1, 2\}$), which both exhibit arbitrary but distinct material properties \bullet_i . The subscript i denotes the corresponding phase. Fig. 2b shows the computational spatial domain Ω , which can be subdivided into the time-dependent sets $\Omega_i(t)$ of a single phase. The curve Γ_{PCI} marks the phase change interface.

In this project paper we will use the *level-set method* (C) to distinguish between phases. Here the basic idea is to use a scalar function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ as an indicator for the phase. The level-set method is described in Section 2.3.

Knowing the phase at each location and time (\mathbf{x}, t) means we can update the material parameters upon which our governing equations depend. We can then solve the governing equations to get updated information on the flow (A) and temperature field (B).

Having introduced the physical two-phase problem conceptually, we may now proceed with its mathematical description.

2.1. Governing Equations

In this project paper we consider an incompressible non-isothermal two-phase problem. We call the spatial domain $\Omega = \Omega_1(t) \cup \Omega_2(t)$ where $\Omega_i(t)$ describe the parts of the domain that contain a single phase. The interface between the two phases is thus given by $\Gamma_{PCI}(t) = \partial\Omega_1(t) \cap \partial\Omega_2(t)$ (see Fig. 2b). Note the time dependency of $\Omega_i(t)$ and $\Gamma_{PCI}(t)$ since the PCI, and thus also the curve $\Gamma_{PCI}(t)$, vary over time. We call the (fixed) exterior boundary of the spatial domain Γ_Ω .

Figure 3: A simplified flowchart showing the basic flow of information for the numerical solution at a single time instance. The solution of the flow and temperature field (**A** and **B**) requires global knowledge of the current phase prevailing at each location \mathbf{x} in the domain, since we assume that the material properties (like density ρ , viscosity μ , thermal conductivity k ...) depend on the phase. The level-set problem (**C**) is solved to indicate the phase but the computation of the level-set velocity in turn requires knowledge about the heat flux at the PCI.

At each instant $t \in (0, t_{total}]$, the velocity, $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the pressure, $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and the temperature, $T(\mathbf{x}, t)$, in each phase i in subdomain $\Omega_i(t)$ are governed by the following equations [14]:

$$\text{Incompressible Navier-Stokes} \quad \rho_i \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{f} \right) - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i = \mathbf{0}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Continuity} \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Stress Tensor} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i(\mathbf{u}, p) = -p\mathbf{I} + 2\mu_i \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}), \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Strain Tensor} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Transient Heat Equation} \quad \rho_i (c_p)_i \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T \right) = k_i \nabla^2 T \quad (5)$$

where ρ_i is the density, μ_i is the dynamic viscosity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$ denotes the stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u})$ stands for the rate-of-strain tensor and $(c_p)_i$ implies the isobaric heat capacity, which is assumed to be constant. Moreover, k_i is the thermal conductivity. Here the indexing $i = 1, 2$ again represents the current phase, which can be either liquid or solid for melting problems.

Table 1 links the governing equations to the unknowns and the algorithm steps introduced in Fig. 3. Note that while we have previously stated the solution of the flow field (**A**) and the temperature (**B**) in the diagram in Fig. 3 to be strongly coupled, we only observe weak coupling in the absence of buoyancy terms as presented in Eqn. (1).

Primal Unknown	Flow Field	Temperature Field	Level-Set Function
<i>Index</i>	A	B	C
<i>Variables</i>	$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t), p(\mathbf{x}, t)$	$T(\mathbf{x}, t)$	$\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$
<i>Gouverning Eqn.</i>	INS Eqn. (1), Eqn. (2)	Transient Heat Eqn. Eqn. (5)	Level-Set Eqn. Eqns. (6a-6b)

Table 1: Quick overview of the governing equations.

It is thus possible to first bring velocity \mathbf{u} and pressure p to convergence solving only Eqn. (1) - Eqn. (2) and then solve for the temperature field (Eqn. (5)). This is to be regarded as a simplifying assumption and in general flow and temperature can be strongly coupled.

2.2. Numerical Methods for Multi-Phase Problems

From the problem description shown above it becomes clear that, in order to solve the system of governing equations, we need information about the phase $i \in \{1, 2\} = \{\text{liquid}, \text{solid}\}$ in order to apply the correct material parameters at each location \mathbf{x} in the domain Ω .

The need for accurate simulations of multi-phase flows gave rise to a variety of numerical methods, of which a brief review can be found in [6]. For phase change from liquid to solid (solidification) and solid to liquid (melting), an overview can be found in [15]. In general, a distinction can be made between two approaches:

In *interface tracking* methods the interface between two phases is explicitly resolved by the discretization of the domain. This implies that grid points lie on the moving interface which in turn requires continuous remeshing at the interface. One application of explicit interface tracking in boiling flows is documented in [16].

On the other hand, *interface capturing* methods implicitly track the interface, typically using some kind of indicator function containing information about the phase at each location [6]. Here it is worth mentioning the *volume of fluid* approach, where the volume share contained in a discrete element to be attributed to each phase is tracked [17], [18]. This method is mostly used in the context of finite volume discretizations but has disadvantages when an evaluation of the geometry of the interface is required [19]. Other approaches are *enthalpy methods* [20] and *level-set methods*.

2.3. The Level-Set Method

The following section closely follows the review in [21].

The *level-set method* has been introduced in the late '80s [7] and has been proven successful in the description of two-phase flows. As shown in Fig. 5, the scalar level-set function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is computed at each point in the domain and its sign is used as an indicator for the phase associated with each location. Subsequently, the curve of zero level-set marks the boundary between the two phases and we thus define the curve $\Gamma_{\text{PCI}} = \{\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0\}$. The question now becomes how the scalar Φ and with it the PCI is transported in the presence of phase change. The level-set equation

$$\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0 \quad (6a)$$

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \Phi_0(\mathbf{x}) \quad (6b)$$

describes this scalar advection problem. The key quantity of interest here is the advection velocity $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, which has to be chosen appropriately in order to describe the physics of phase change. In fact, a major part of this report will be dedicated to the question of how to accurately compute \mathbf{v} (see Section 2.4 and following).

The initial condition $\Phi_0(\mathbf{x})$ is chosen such that $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the signed distance function with respect to the PCI. It is desirable to keep this property as Φ evolves over time, since it allows for an easy evaluation of geometric properties such as the normal \mathbf{n} to the phase-change interface Γ_{PCI}

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\nabla \Phi}{\|\nabla \Phi\|}, \quad (7)$$

which points in the direction of the gradient of Φ . Such a signed distance initialization Φ_0 is shown in Fig. 4 for the example of a circular PCI. In some applications such as dendritic solidification [10] the curvature k of the interface is also of interest:

$$k = \text{div} \frac{\nabla \Phi}{\|\nabla \Phi\|}. \quad (8)$$

This conceptual simplicity of the level-set method and the relative ease of implementation even in multi-dimensional settings both attribute to the method's popularity. We also note the following favourable properties:

The level-set method is

- relatively easy to describe mathematically. The level-set equation is a standard scalar advection equation, for which solution methods have been exhaustively studied in literature.

- capable of representing sharp interfaces. Mushy phase transitions can be implemented using a smoothing kernel.
- suitable for applications where the geometry of the interface is of interest [19]. The interface curvature and normals can be computed directly from the level-set function.
- operating on fixed grids.

Level-Set Reinitialization

The aforementioned geometrical properties are an advantage of this particular level-set initialization and one of the reasons why keeping the signed distance property over time is desirable. For the coupling of the level-set with the underlying physical problem we are only interested in the **sign** of the level-set function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$. It is therefore a common practice to reinitialize Φ using the signed distance with respect to the current phase-change interface (refer to the circular red curve in Fig. 4) after a certain number of time steps.

In a numerical setting computing the signed distance with respect to the curve Γ_{PCI} means computing the shortest distance to the interface of all nodal points on the numerical grid. The most naive implementation of this operation thus has a complexity of

$$\mathcal{O}(n_{\text{grid}} \cdot n_{\text{PCI}}) \quad (9)$$

where n_{grid} denotes the total number of mesh nodes and n_{PCI} is the number of interface *crossings* with the mesh.

A popular algorithm solving this problem more efficiently is the fast-marching method [22], but since its implementation is beyond the scope of this project we will rely on the more simplistic approach introduced above. As a side note we can state that the cost of reinitialization has been proven to be negligible compared to the computational cost of solving for the flow and temperature field, at least for the small and moderately sized meshes considered in this project. This is also due to the fact that the reinitialization algorithm has to be called at most once per time step. Nevertheless the additional overhead introduced by the reinitialization procedure remains a drawback of the level-set method, especially for more complex (3D) meshes.

Figure 4: Signed distance Φ_0 for a circular curve Γ_0 shown in red. The circle is centered at the origin $O = (0, 0, 0)^T$. In the context of a level-set initialization we could use Φ_0 as an initial value for the level set function $\Phi(x, y)$. In that case Γ_0 would be the PCI and the exterior (positive level-set) and interior (negative level-set) of the red circle in the $x - y$ plane would correspond to phases 1 and 2 respectively. As shown in Fig. 4b, the normal vector \mathbf{n} points in the direction of the gradient of Φ_0 .

2.4. Computation of Melting Velocities

Thus far we have set up a mathematical formulation (Eqn. (6a)) for the transport of the level-set, which encodes information about the local phase at each point in the domain. Fig. 6 shows the level-set transport over time for a fictitious configuration of phases. Since the curve of zero level-set Γ_{PCI} (the red curve in Fig. 6) marks the boundary between phases, it is intuitively clear that the velocity \mathbf{v}_{PCI} (black arrows in Fig. 6) at this interface should correspond to the physical velocity of the phase change process. For a transition from solid to liquid we call this velocity the *melting velocity* \mathbf{U} .

To arrive at a full description of our solution method we will need to introduce a closure for the melting velocity which essentially provides a link between the algorithmic concept of a level-set method and the physics of melting.

(a) Numerical Level-Set Domain

(b) Two-Phase Level-Set

Figure 5: Numerical (left) and physical (right) view of the two-phase level-set problem. On the left (Fig. 5a) the domain introduced in Fig. 2 is discretized by a structured grid. The sign of the scalar level set function $\Phi = \Phi(x, t)$, $x \in \Omega$ is used as an indicator for the phase at each node of the grid. The curve of zero-level set is used as an approximation of the PCI. The Figure on the right (Fig. 5b) shows a physical interpretation in the context of a melting problem.

Figure 6: Convective transport of the PCI over time. The left and right hand figure show the initial and the advected PCI respectively. In the context of level-set methods the movement of the PCI is interpreted as a displacement of the curve Γ_{PCI} which corresponds to the line of zero level set $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$. The arrows indicate the interface velocity $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}_{PCI}, t) = \mathbf{v}_{PCI}$ at different locations $\mathbf{x}_{PCI} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega \mid \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0\}$ on the PCI, which is given as the melting velocity $\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

The Stefan Problem

An elementary model for a **1D transient phase change problem** is the Stefan problem [23]. The 1D Stefan problem considers a domain which, initially in a solid state, gets heated from one boundary at a temperature $T > T_m$, with T_m denoting the melting temperature ($273.15K$ for water). It relates the translation of the boundary $X(t)$ between a molten liquid phase and a solid phase, called phase-change interface (PCI), with the heat fluxes at the liquid (q_L) and the solid (q_S) side of the interface:

$$\rho h_m \frac{\partial}{\partial t} X(t) = -k_L \frac{\partial T(X(t), t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} X(t)-h} + k_S \frac{\partial T(X(t), t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} X(t)+h} \equiv q_L - q_S. \quad (10)$$

Fig. 7 sketches the corresponding setup and the position of the PCI.

Figure 7: Sketch of the 1D Stefan problem along a semi-infinite rectangular slab. The initial condition is shown on the left. The image on the right shows the system at a time $t > 0$ with the PCI at position $X(t)$. Figure recreated after Figure 2.1 of [24].

Defining the melting velocity as $U(\mathbf{x}, t) := \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}, t})}{\partial t}$, the above statement can be generalized to multi-dimensional phase-change:

$$\rho h_m U(\mathbf{x}, t) = \underbrace{-k_L \nabla T \Big|_{X^-}}_{q_L} + \underbrace{k_S \nabla T \Big|_{X^+}}_{-q_S} \quad =: [k \nabla T]_L^S \quad (11a)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow U(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\rho h_m} [k \nabla T]_L^S. \quad (11b)$$

Here we introduce the notation $X^\pm := \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} X(t) \pm h$ for the limit taken from either side of the PCI (e.g. liquid or solid). The bracket notation $[\bullet]_a^b$ is used to denote a jump of quantity \bullet from state a to b , subsequently we write

$$q_L - q_S = [k \nabla T]_L^S \quad (12)$$

for the *jump in the heat flux* from liquid (L) to solid (S) phase.

The Stefan condition is of utmost importance in the description of our numerical method since it provides a closure condition for the advection velocity of the curve Γ_{PCI} . Knowing the discontinuity in the heat flux, which, by Fourier's law, is directly proportional to the jump in the temperature gradient (see Eqn. (12)) we can directly compute $v_{\text{PCI}} \equiv \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t)$ by means of Eqn. (11b). However, this strategy strongly relies on the assumption that an accurate recovery of the temperature gradient is obtainable through our numerical solution method for the temperature field. Moreover, we also need to be able to *resolve discontinuities* in the temperature derivative.

Level-Set Methods for Finite Elements

While the level-Set method had been mostly applied to finite difference discretizations originally [7], there also exist documented attempts at using finite elements [11] [12]. Finite element methods (FEM) are well-suited for the discretization of complex geometries and are a standard numerical tool for the solution of partial differential equations. For a general introduction to FEM the curious reader shall be referred to [25]. The referred book includes reviews of standard Galerkin finite element methods (Chapters 1.5 and 2.2) and space-time finite element methods (Chapter 3.10) which are employed in this project.

While we will use FEM to solve the governing equations (Eqns. 1-5)), the goal of this project work is not to give an in-depth description of the FEM assembly and problem statement. To keep the following explanations accessible, we will rather focus on basic properties of residual based methods.

For simplicity consider $u(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathcal{S}$ to be the exact solution to a well-posed, scalar initial value boundary problem lying in a solution space \mathcal{S} . In Galerkin FEM we numerically compute an approximation $u_n^h(\mathbf{x})$ of $u(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ at each discrete time step t^n in a lower-order space \mathcal{S}^h of interpolation functions $N(x)$. A common procedure is to choose interpolation functions in space and then apply numerical time integration to compute the evolution of $u_n^h(\mathbf{x})$ over time (semi-discrete FEM). Fig. 8 shows the very basic example of piece-wise linear 1D interpolation functions. The numerical approximation $u_n^h(\mathbf{x})$ at time t^n is then as a linear combination of the interpolation basis

$$u^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n) = \sum_{A=1}^{n_\Omega} N_A(\mathbf{x}) u_A^n \quad (13)$$

Here we consider the n_Ω grid nodes with degrees of freedom u_A .

In the Space-Time FEM however, the temporal dependency is integrated explicitly in the interpolation space \mathcal{S}^h such that u^h becomes $u^h(\mathbf{x}, t)$. This makes the formulation of the variational form of the governing Eqns. (1-5)) more involved, but has certain

advantages in terms of accuracy and stability especially for moving and deforming meshes.

We decided to cut short on the explanation of space-time FEM in this project paper. For a more thorough introduction please be referred to Chapter 3.10 of [25] and [26].

Note that the strategy for flux recovery proposed hereinafter it is not limited to Space-Time FEM and we will thus stick with the slightly more simple case of a space-only FEM discretization as in Eqn. (13) for its description.

Figure 8: 1D Linear FEM shape functions $N(x)$ (top) and their element-wise constant derivatives (bottom) on a uniform discretization with grid nodes at locations x_i . In this example all shape functions are zero on the boundary of the domain (see $x_0 = 0$). Shape function derivatives $\frac{dN}{dx}$ are discontinuous only on element nodes.

3. Flux Reconstruction and Ghost Split with FEM

In this chapter we will demonstrate a method for the recovery of the heat flux discontinuity at the [PCI](#) using finite element methods with element-wise continuously differentiable shape functions. Existing algorithms successfully using a similar strategy have been described in [8], [13] and [9], but these implementations only consider finite-difference discretizations. While the geometry of the interface itself was allowed to be irregular in these publications, the computational domain itself was considered to be regular and discretized using structured grids.

By extending the idea to finite element discretizations we hope to combine the versatility of [FEM](#) in terms of possible domain geometries with the conceptual simplicity of the level-set method without the need for more complex choices of [FEM](#) shape functions or local enrichment of the [FEM](#) basis. In particular this allows us to keep the total number of degrees of freedom constant over time, meaning that we don't need to alter the size of the global system matrix. This can be an advantage especially in heavily parallelized [FEM](#) codes.

For the sake of easier visualization we will restrict the following explanations to a structured mesh, but we explicitly note here that all concepts should be equally applicable for the unstructured case. A showcase of a melting problem on an unstructured mesh will be provided in Section 4.3. Fig. 9 provides a link between the numerical domain with associated level-set and the local view of a few elements bisected by the [PCI](#). The intersection points (red crosses) are implicitly given by the condition $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$. We compute these points from the value of the level-set function Φ at the nodes adjacent to the cut element face (points highlighted in Fig. 9) by linear interpolation. Nodes on either side of the [PCI](#) are uniquely associated with one of the distinct phases.

In the following sections we will explain how to compute an approximation of the melting velocity at the intersection points with element faces corresponding to the location of the zero level-set. For this task the nodes adjacent to the element face on either side of the interface (solid blue dots and red circles in Fig. 9) are of special interest.

3.1. Gradient Recovery

As we have demonstrated in the previous paragraphs, the melting velocity is a function of the flux discontinuity at the phase change interface. By Fourier's law the discontinuity in the heat flux is expressed as a discontinuity in the gradient of temperature at the [PCI](#), which we denoted by

$$\left[q \right]_L^S = \left[k \nabla T \right]_L^S.$$

Figure 9: Structured mesh bisected by the interface between two phases. The zoomed in view shows the intersection of four quadratic elements. The location of the intersection on element faces is indicated by the red crosses (right). As an approximation of the heat flux in both phases at the intersection we consider the flux at the highlighted nodes adjacent to the cut phase.

Let us also recall that the reason we are interested in this jump was to compute the melting velocity at the interface location \mathbf{x}_{PCI}

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t) \equiv \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t) = \frac{1}{\rho h_m} \left[k \nabla T \right]_L^S. \quad (14)$$

which in turn will be used as an advection velocity in the level-set Eqn. 6b. In consequence, we hope to use the numerical approximation $T^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ of the real temperature field $T(\mathbf{x}, t)$ obtained from the FEM solution of Eqn. (5) to evaluate the jump condition and close this problem. Fig. 10 shows a fictitious exact 1D temperature profile (purple dashed line) which exhibits a kink (a discontinuity in the derivative) at the location of the PCI ($\Phi(x) = 0$), where it takes on the value of the melting temperature T_M . The continuous orange line represents a numerical temperature solution $T^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ (with $\mathbf{x} \equiv x$ in 1D) obtained on an equidistant 1D grid at the given time instance t^n .

Following Eqn. (13) we write the numerical temperature solution in terms of the degrees of freedom

$$T^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n) = \sum_{A=1}^{n_\Omega} N_A(\mathbf{x}) u_{A,T}^n. \quad (15)$$

Figure 10: Piece-wise linear approximation $T^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ (orange line) of a fictitious exact temperature profile T_{real} (purple dashed line). The central element of the uniform grid is bisected by the phase change interface (PCI) at $\Phi(x) = 0$, with grid nodes located to the left ($\Phi(x) < 0$) and right ($\Phi(x) > 0$) belonging to different phases.

with FEM interpolation functions $N_A(\mathbf{x})$ and the nodal temperature degrees of freedom $u_{A,T}^n$. Subsequently the gradient of the numerical temperature field is given by

$$\nabla T^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n) = \sum_{A=1}^{n_\Omega} \nabla N_A(\mathbf{x}) u_{A,T}^n \quad (16)$$

meaning that we shift the derivative onto the interpolation function. It thus becomes clear that the mathematical properties of the numerical gradient $\nabla T^h(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ are dictated by the shape and form of the interpolation function. In particular it will not exhibit discontinuities, unless they are specifically built into the interpolation space S^h . The most common choices of interpolation functions, such as piece-wise linear or piece-wise quadratic functions, are however element-wise continuously differentiable.

For illustration consider Fig. 11. Here the 1D mesh element e_c is bisected by the PCI. We are interested in the melting velocity v , knowing that in 1D the interface can only move either to the left or to the right. To evaluate Eqn. (14) we need to decide on a representative flux

$$\bar{q}_i := k_i \nabla T|_i \stackrel{(1D)}{=} k_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \Big|_i, \quad i \in \{L, S\} \quad (17)$$

at the interface in the limit from solid (S) and liquid (L) side, allowing us to rewrite Eqn. (14) in terms of \bar{q}_i as

$$v(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t) \equiv \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\rho h_m} \left[k \nabla T \right]_L^S \stackrel{(17)}{\approx} \frac{1}{\rho h_m} (\bar{q}_L - \bar{q}_S). \quad (18)$$

It becomes evident from Fig. 11b, that for piece-wise linear interpolation functions the recovered gradient $\frac{\partial T_c}{\partial x}$ will be constant across the cut element e_c and thus no jump can be computed from the numerical solution directly on the interface, implying $v \equiv 0$.

Figure 11: Recovery of derivatives at the nodes n_1 and n_2 (red circles in Fig. 11a). Our goal is to compute the advection velocity v of the interface (vertical red dashed line) / the melting velocity U at $\Phi = 0$, which requires an approximation of the discontinuity in the heat flux at the interface. Since the interface cuts the element e_c , the flux at the adjacent nodes n_1 and n_2 serves as a representative for the flux in each phase at the interface location. Using the numerical temperature solution $T^h(x)$ we recover the temperature gradient, which, by using linear (first order) interpolation functions, corresponds to the constant slope within the elements e_1 , e_c and e_2 . The recovered gradient $\frac{\partial T_c}{\partial x}$ at the cut element e_c can however never be discontinuous since such shape functions are by construction element-wise continuously differentiable.

Extended finite element methods (XFEM) provide a remedy to this drawback of standard finite element formulations. While originally invented as an alternative to remeshing in mechanical problems such as crack propagation [27], the method has also been employed successfully to capture discontinuous gradients in problems of Stefan type [28]. A brief introduction to XFEM in this context can also be found in Chapter 4.3 of [29]. The key idea is to include discontinuities into the solution space by local enrichment of the FEM basis with functions that have discontinuous derivatives. The drawback is however, that one needs to update the nodes that are enriched based on

the location of the interface. This implies that the total number of degrees of freedom is constantly changing over time.

For the existing parallel software [XNS](#) that this project is embedded in the implementation overhead for [XFEM](#) would have been significant. We thus aim to find an alternative computationally cheap and conceptually simple method of recovering flux discontinuities with standard choices of [FEM](#) basis functions.

3.2. Flux Nodes for FEM Meshes

The choice of evaluation points for the representative fluxes \bar{q}_i (as in Eqn. (17)) is highly influential for the accurate determination of the melting velocity. The key requirement here is that the flux \bar{q}_i converges to the flux at the interface in the limit for fine mesh resolutions. Furthermore the evaluation strategy for the flux should be as general as possible, not being limited by the type of mesh or choice of basis function. Different strategies to compute the gradient at either side of the interface such as one-sided finite-differencing stencils have been proposed in literature [10], [29], but in the general case of [FEM](#) these methods lack applicability. Fig. 12 shows different cases of elements on a structured grid being cut by the [PCI](#). The red crosses mark the location of the cut on element phases. Different choices of representative evaluation locations for the temperature gradient suffer from different issues:

- along a cut element face, e.g. a face marked by a red cross, the derivative might be constant within a single adjacent element but different to the derivative computed at the second adjacent element,
- if one was to evaluate the derivative at a point normal to the interface it is unclear where exactly this point should lie. For a linear [PCI](#) reconstruction as in Fig. 12 the normal to the interface is not well defined at the crossings with element faces (red crosses),
- the evaluation of the temperature solution at an arbitrary point in the domain is not exactly straightforward, since it requires a global mapping from arbitrary physical coordinates to local element coordinates.

To circumvent the aforementioned difficulties we propose a pragmatic strategy for the evaluation of the numerical flux. It consists of the following three propositions:

1. For an element face cut by the [PCI](#), consider the nodes that comprise this face as **flux nodes**, which means that we will use the recovered numerical flux at these nodes as the representative fluxes \bar{q}_i to compute the approximate melting velocity **at the crossing** using Eqn. (18). Based on the nodal value of the level set function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ we can determine whether this node is associated with the liquid phase, yielding the representative flux \bar{q}_L (e.g. the blue solid nodes in Fig. 12), or the solid phase with flux \bar{q}_S (red circular markers).

2. The nodal gradient is recovered using a least-squares fitting based on the gradient within all elements adjacent to a mesh node. Consider for example the central node in Fig. 12a-Fig. 12d. This node would yield as a nodal gradient an average of the gradient at the four square elements surrounding it. For piece-wise linear interpolation functions this reduces to an averaging of the element-wise constant gradients (refer also to Fig. 11b for the 1D case).
3. For the special case of a mesh node being intersected by the PCI (see Fig. 12d) we consider the average flux of all adjacent nodes in each face to obtain \bar{q}_L and \bar{q}_S respectively.

Figure 12: Recovery of the flux jump at a PCI cutting a structured mesh. Red crosses mark the intersection points of the interface (red dashed line) with element faces. The highlighted element nodes are the nodes that are involved in the computation of the approximate heat flux at the intersection point cutting an adjacent face. Here the blue solid dots indicate nodes belonging to phase 1 (left) and the red circles mark nodes associated with phase 2 (right). Fig. 12d shows a special case where a mesh node is cut by the PCI.

We have now decided on a strategy to find representative fluxes to evaluate the Stefan condition and find the melting velocity which will be used as the advection velocity for the level-set field. Unfortunately, we reckon the representative fluxes (and subse-

quently the melting velocity) to be of little accuracy without an adequate remedy for the problem of resolving the gradient discontinuity as described in Section 3.1.

3.3. The Ghost Split

In the following section we build upon ideas from [8], [13] and [9], to describe a conceptually simple method to capture discontinuous derivatives in phase change problems with standard Galerkin FEM. The proposed strategy will allow for straightforward implementation and does not require an adaptive change of the FEM basis, meaning that the system matrix for the resulting linear system of equations will remain of constant size. We also do not add computational overhead compared to the FEM solution of the coupled Navier-Stokes Eqn. (1), transient heat Eqn. (5) and Level-Set Eqn. (6a).

As previously discussed, standard FEM interpolation functions that are continuously differentiable across elements are, by construction, not able to represent discontinuous first derivatives in elements cut by the PCI. With piece-wise linear shape functions such discontinuities in the gradient ∇T^h of the numerical solution T^h can subsequently only occur at element nodes (see Fig. 8). The idea of the *ghost split* is founded upon the observation, that the numerical temperature approximations T_i^h with $i \in \{L, S\}$ in liquid (L) and solid (S) phase essentially uncouple. Since the physics of melting always require that the temperature solution takes on the value of the temperature T_M at the phase-change interface, e.g. $T^h(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t) \stackrel{!}{=} T_M$ at all times t , the PCI can be viewed as a Dirichlet boundary to either of the adjacent phases.

Fig. 13 shows a conceptual ghost split for the 1D problem we introduced in Section 3.1. Since we know that the center element is intersected by the PCI (vertical dashed red line) we can infer that the temperature profile should satisfy

$$T^h(x_{\text{PCI}}, t) = T_M \quad (19)$$

at the position of the cut. Knowing this interface condition, the temperature approximations T^h on the split domains $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,2}$ with $\Omega = \Omega_{T,1} \cup \Omega_{T,2}$ uncouple in the sense that no knowledge about the temperature profile in the second phase other than the location of the PCI is necessary. The idea is thus to solve independent temperature problems T_1^h and T_2^h in each phase and use the gradients recovered from the individual problems to compute the melting velocity, proceeding as described in Section 3.1.

Since we can only prescribe boundary conditions as local degrees of freedom on mesh nodes (e.g. prescribe the value of u_A^n in Eqn. (13)), imposing the melting temperature at the interface manifests in the concept of *ghost nodes*. The term refers to the fact that we are adding additional nodes to the split subdomain to enforce the temperature boundary condition from Eqn. 19 at the approximate position of the interface. The ghost nodes n_1 and n_2 in our 1D example are marked by the red rhombi in Fig. 13.

They are used as a Dirichlet boundary to the two split temperature problems T_1^h and T_2^h respectively to impose the temperature of melting T_M .

As a consequence of the ghost split technique and the melting temperature being enforced not at the exact location of the PCI, but at a nearby ghost node, we introduce an error in the interface location computed at later time steps. We observe however that in the limit of finer spatial mesh resolutions (as $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$), the position of the ghost node will converge to the correct interface location. By solving two FEM problems with Dirichlet boundaries on the ghost nodes we are furthermore able to recover discontinuous temperature gradients across the approximate position of the PCI. We obtain an approximation of the flux at either side of the interface by a gradient recovery using the corresponding split temperature solution T_i^h .

(a) Ghost split domain for the left phase

(b) Ghost split domain for the right phase

Figure 13: 1D Ghost Split. We split the domain into two subdomains $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,2}$ based on the phase information encoded in the sign of the level-set. The temperature problems T_1 and T_2 are independently solved, but couple through the Dirichlet *ghost nodes* (red rhombi), where we prescribe the melting temperature T_M . In this example the node n_2 would be the ghost node for the domain $\Omega_{T,1}$ (Fig. 13a) and n_1 is the ghost node for $\Omega_{T,2}$ (Fig. 13b). By prescribing the melting temperature not at the exact location of the PCI (red vertical line), but on the nodes adjacent to the cut mesh face, we at most distort the predicted interface location by $\mathcal{O}(\Delta x)$.

The accuracy of the predicted interface depends on the exact value prescribed as a Dirichlet boundary value at the ghost nodes. In the previous example, as well as in the following computations, we resolve to the most simple case of *constant* extrapolation of the melting temperature T_M . Following the argument in [8] we note that this corresponds to a $\mathcal{O}(\Delta x)$ disturbance in the interface position. By imposing the melting temperature at a ghost node adjacent to the cut face we at most dislocate the cut by one element length. Note that unlike the structured grid used in [8], the element face length may vary across the mesh on arbitrary unstructured grids. The convergence of the algorithm for a 1D Stefan problem is shown in Section 4.1.

(a) Subdomain of the first phase, $\Phi < 0$ (b) Subdomain of the second phase, $\Phi > 0$

Figure 14: 2D ghost split of the temperature domain. The total computational domain Ω of the two-phase problem is split into separate domains $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,2}$ for the temperature solution based on the level-set function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$. The melting temperature T_M is imposed as a Dirichlet boundary condition for the two subproblems at the *ghost nodes* marked by red rhombi.

Fig. 14 extends the ghost split to the introductory 2D example of a two phase problem, showing the two temperature domains $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,2}$ split by the zero level-set (red curve). The ghost nodes where the temperature of melting T_M is imposed as a Dirichlet boundary condition for the two independent problems are marked by the red rhombi adjacent to the interface. Note that the overall number of nodes on which we are solving for the temperature field (the mesh nodes that are not highlighted and thus not part of any boundary) does not change compared to the original discretization shown for example in Fig. 9.

Temperature Extrapolation and Skipped Nodes

Before we present numerical results obtained with our implementation of the ghost split, we would like to briefly touch on two more advanced aspects of the method described in this project paper.

As shown in Fig. 13, we extrapolated the phase-change temperature T_M from its exact location on the PCI onto a neighbouring mesh node to uncouple the temperature domains of two phases. This node was then marked as part of a Dirichlet boundary for one of the phases. By shifting the physical boundary condition $T = T_M$ at $x = x_{\text{PCI}}$

onto a node adjacent to the cut face, we essentially assumed the temperature to be constant within the cut element (*constant extrapolation*). As discussed in [9], one can think of higher order extrapolation schemes to shift the location at which the numerical temperature solution T^h satisfies $T^h(\mathbf{x}, t) = T_M$ closer to the computed position of the PCI. Within the scope of this project we experimented with linear extrapolation but faced difficulties with ill-behavedness of the resulting temperature solution.

A second remark should be dedicated to the issue of *skipped nodes*. For the following explanation we again fall back to the 1D case of a two-phase problem. In Fig. 15 we consider the same split temperature domains shown before, with emphasis on the left hand side domain $\Omega_{T,1}$. After having computed the advection velocity \mathbf{v} at a certain time t^n (using fluxes at nodes n_1 and n_2), we are able to compute the interface shift and the new location of the PCI (Fig. 15b). However, if the shift of the PCI (red vertical dashed line) is too large, it will potentially jump over mesh nodes that had previously not be included in the computational subdomain. In our example this affects the mesh nodes n_2 and n_3 , which become part of the computational domain $\Omega_{T,1}^+$ at the next time step t^{n+1} after the shift. This gives rise to the question how to treat such new nodes. One approach is described in section 4.1.1. of [9], where the authors propose to use an extrapolation of the numerical temperature solution T^h in normal direction to the interface. The generalized higher order extrapolation scheme used in [9] requires the solution of a sequence of advection problems [30] though and therefore adds to the overall computational and conceptual complexity of the algorithm at hand.

For this project we thus decided to refrain from implementing a global extrapolation scheme of any kind and resolved to an optional adaptive restriction of the time step size. This can essentially be thought of as a CFL-like condition: Since at a given time step t^n we have a priori knowledge about our mesh structure and the maximum advection velocity at any location on the interface

$$v_{\max}(t^n) := \max_{\mathbf{x}, t^n} \|\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t^n)\|, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \quad (20)$$

after the evaluation of nodal fluxes (see previous Section 3.1), we can avoid skipping over more than a single node by choosing the next time step $\Delta t^{n+1} = t^{n+1} - t^n$ to satisfy

$$\Delta t^{n+1} \leq \frac{h_{\min}}{v_{\max}(t^n)}. \quad (21)$$

Here h_{\min} denotes the (global) minimum element face length.

3.4. Velocity Extension

In Section 3.1 and Section 3.2 we discussed how to compute the melting velocity $U(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t^n)$ at the approximate location of the interface. To solve the level-set Eqn. (6a)

Figure 15: Node skipping for a split domain. At a time step t^n a melting or interface advection velocity v is computed using the heat flux at ghost nodes n_1 and n_2 for the split domains $\Omega_{T,2}$ and $\Omega_{T,1}$ respectively (Fig. 15a). If the displacement of the interface $\Delta x_{\text{PCI}} = v \cdot (t^{n+1} - t^n)$ is too large, the PCI may skip over nodes, which become part of the new temperature domain $\Omega_{T,1}^+$ for the left phase at the next time instance t^{n+1} (Fig. 15b). In this example this affects the nodes n_2 and n_3 .

$$\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$$

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \Phi_0(\mathbf{x})$$

it is however necessary to define the advection velocity field $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ at a given time step t^n on all nodes of the computational mesh. This can be achieved by extending the velocity computed in the vicinity of the interface in the direction normal to the PCI, which corresponds to a constant extrapolation along the interface normal [10].

Fig. 16 shows a reconstructed interface (red dashed-dot line), which is piece-wise linear between the cut with element faces C_1 to C_5 at a sample time t^n . In general we consider n_{PCI} such cuts or element crossings (with index $i \in \{1, \dots, n_{\text{PCI}}\}$) on a mesh with n_{grid} nodes (with index $j \in \{1, \dots, n_{\text{grid}}\}$). In the previous sections we discussed how to find an approximate melting velocity at the position of the cuts. We now pose the question how to extend this velocity onto all nodes, to construct the level-set velocity field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$. Since the normal of the interface is not well-defined at the crossings (the linear reconstruction has a kink at the cuts C_i) we simply use a nearest neighbour classification to decide for all mesh nodes n_j which value of $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}_j, t^n)$ to prescribe at the nodal position \mathbf{x}_j . That is we prescribe the value of the melting velocity $U(\mathbf{x}_{C,i}, t^n)$ computed at the crossing C_i at all nodes that are closest to this crossing.

In Fig. 16 all grid nodes n_j (black dots) on a structured mesh are marked by the shape of the interface crossing C_i located closest to the node. The value of the advection velocity $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}_j, t^n)$ at the respective nodal position \mathbf{x}_j is then chosen to be equivalent

Figure 16: Extension strategy for the approximate melting velocity computed at cuts C_1 to C_5 of the phase change interface with element face on a structured sample mesh. The five different crossings are distinguishable by the shape of their black markers. The advection velocity $v(\mathbf{x}_j, t^n)$ prescribed at the twelve grid points n_j (black dots) corresponds to the interface velocity at the closest crossing. This affiliation is indicated by the thin dotted lines and the (coloured) shapes on the nodes. The velocity of the PCI at the cut location \mathbf{x}_i for each individual crossing C_i is approximated by means of the algorithm described in Section 3.1.

to the interface velocity computed at the closest crossing. For example the velocity $U(\mathbf{x}_{C,1}, t^n)$ computed at the crossing C_1 is assigned to the node in the upper left corner of the mesh because the crossing C_1 is the closest element cut out of the crossings C_1 to C_5 . The affiliation of nodes with the closest crossing is also indicated by the dotted lines.

The extension strategy implemented in this project deviates slightly from the proposition in [10], where a scalar advection problem in the direction of the interface normal is solved for each component of the melting velocity on the interface. It is however based on the same idea, because assigning at each mesh node the velocity of the closest crossing is essentially a cheap approximation of a constant extrapolation in normal direction. Note that we do not require an additional search for the nearest neighbour on the PCI, since we already conduct this search in the reinitialization step for the level-set function (see Section 2.3).

Before we present numerical results let us briefly summarize the above algorithm. The solution of the two-phase problem with a ghost-split level-set method boils down to the following steps:

1. Initialize the level-set function. The zero level-set at the starting time represents the initial geometry of the PCI,

2. Update the material parameters according to the phase information encoded in the sign of the level set function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$. Use the **FEM** to solve the system of governing equations (Eqns. (1-5)) at time t^n to obtain numerical solutions for the unknown velocity, pressure and temperature at all mesh nodes.
3. Based on the level-set function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ compute the location of the interface \mathbf{x}_{PCI} . This is equivalent to finding the curve of zero level-set ($\Phi(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}}, t^n) = 0$).
4. Find the approximate melting velocity $\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{PCI}})$ at the crossings of the **PCI** hyper-plane with the **FEM** mesh.
5. Extend the melting velocity at the crossings onto all mesh nodes to obtain the level-set advection velocity $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$. At the same time, reinitialize the level-set function such that $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t^n) = \Phi_0(\mathbf{x}, t^{n+1})$ corresponds to the signed distance function with respect to the current **PCI**.
6. Solve the level-set equation (Eqns. (6a-6b)) with this new information about the phase at each location. Repeat from step 2 for the consecutive time instance t^{n+1} .

4. Numerical Results

In this chapter we present three numerical test cases for the solution algorithm described in the previous sections.

As a first validation test case we consider the quasi 1D single-phase Stefan problem, where we check our numerical prediction of the melting interface location against an analytical solution. The second simulation is a numerical showcase of the coupling between the solution of level-set, heat equation and incompressible Navier-Stokes equation. In the last simulation we show solidification on an unstructured grid and demonstrate that the numerical solution satisfies an equilibrium condition after some time.

4.1. Validation: Single-Phase Stefan Problem

For a first validation of our code we consider the 1D example of a single-phase Stefan problem. Fig. 17 shows a sketch of the problem setup. A quasi-infinite slab of solid ice at the melting temperature T_M is heated at the left boundary $\partial\Omega_D$ which is kept at a (constant) temperature $T(x=0, t) = T_L > T_M$. As a consequence the ice starts to melt and the melting front (PCI) propagates to the right. We denote the total displacement of the PCI from the left wall as $s(t)$.

Figure 17: Sketch of the simulation setup for the single-phase Stefan problem validation case. The icy phase is kept at a constant melting temperature T_M . The upper and lower boundary are zero-Neumann boundaries, reducing the problem to one dimension. The left boundary $\partial\Omega_D$ is heated at a constant temperature $T_L > T_M$. The transient temperature profile in the liquid phase and the propagation of the PCI are simulated over time.

Since the ice is kept at a constant melting temperature, the heat flux into the ice is zero and the only unknown is the temperature profile in the water. This problem can then be solved analytically using similarity solutions [31] to obtain

$$T(x, t) = T_L - (T_L - T_M) \frac{\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right)}{\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{s(t)}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right)} \quad (22)$$

for the transient temperature profile in the liquid phase. Here α is the thermal diffusivity of the melt and erf is the error function. The (yet unknown) interface location $s(t)$ can be found to be

$$s(t) = 2\sqrt{\alpha} \lambda \sqrt{t}, \quad (23)$$

where the similarity variable λ is found as the unique root to the monotonous function

$$f(\lambda) := \operatorname{Ste} \frac{e^{-\lambda^2}}{\sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(\lambda)} - \lambda. \quad (24)$$

Inserting the Stefan number

$$\operatorname{Ste} := \frac{c_{p,L}(T_L - T_M)}{h_m} \quad (25)$$

and numerically solving $f(\lambda) = 0$ yields $\lambda \approx 0.3915$ for our setup with $T_L = 300 \text{ K}$. The exact parameters used can be found in Table 2.

Test Case Parameters:	Single-Phase Stefan Problem		
wall temperature	T_L	= 300	[K]
latent heat	h_m	= 333700	[J/Kg]
liquid density	ρ_L	= 1000	[Kg/m ³]
liquid heat capacity	$c_{p,L}$	= 4200	[J/(Kg K)]
liquid thermal conductivity	k_L	= 0.6	[W/(m K)]

Table 2: Single phase stefan problem: validation test case parameters.

As a benchmark for the algorithm presented in this thesis we compare the analytical interface location $s(t)$ with our numerically predicted location $\hat{s}(t)$. For an accurate computation of the PCI position we need to

1. correctly solve for the temperature field in the liquid,
2. recover the heat flux at the liquid side of the interface based on the current interface location,

3. solve the level-set equation using the melting velocity as the advection velocity.

Comparing the interface location thus is a test for multiple building blocks of the simulation tool at once. Note that we do not include any flow phenomena yet and thus only the transient heat Eqn. (5) is solved in each time iteration.

Fig. 18 shows the numerically predicted propagation of the melting front (vertical yellow line) on a uniform structured mesh of total length $\Delta L = 1 \text{ cm}$. The initial time is $t = 10 \text{ s}$ and we prescribe the analytical solution $T(x, t = 10 \text{ s})$ from Eqn. (22) as an initial condition for the temperature field (Fig. 18a). The initial interface location is $s(t = 10 \text{ s}) = 0.09358 \text{ cm}$.

As time progresses the interface moves to the right and the liquid melt left of the PCI heats up with the temperature profile being almost linear (quasi-steady melting).

In Fig. 19 we compare the simulated interface location with the analytical prediction (red solid line) for different mesh resolutions. For the highest mesh resolution (black circles) we are able to match the correct position up to accuracies well below 1% (relative error to the analytical solution at the respective time step).

The error propagation is also shown in Fig. 20 over the same time interval. It becomes evident that we can control the error via the spatial resolution.

A first study of spatial convergence is shown in Fig. 21, where we plot the relative error

$$\text{err}_{\text{rel}}(t) = \frac{|s(t) - \hat{s}(t)|}{s(t)} \quad (26)$$

at a fixed time $t = 310 \text{ s}$ far from the initial time for different (uniform) mesh resolutions. The experimental order of convergence (EOC) shown in Fig. 21 is the slope of the linear fit between two consecutive datapoints in the logarithmic error plot

$$EOC_i = \left| \frac{\log(\text{Error}_i) - \log(\text{Error}_{i+1})}{\log(\Delta x_i) - \log(\Delta x_{i+1})} \right|, \quad (27)$$

where Δx is the mesh resolution and the subscript i refers is the index of the datapoint (a combination of mesh resolution and measured error).

For the considered case of 1D melting we observe a worst-case EOC around one and a highest EOC of 2.7. The convergence shown is super-linear, but we note that the simplicity of the test case at least partially attributes to this result. Influence factors such as the flux into the ice (two-phase Stefan problem) and the quality of the choice of representative fluxes for more complex geometries of the PCI are not included and are likely to make for worse convergence rates and accuracies. Nevertheless the results warrant a first validation of the proposed simulation algorithm.

After having tested the basic functionality of our implementation, we would like to present two showcases of 2D melting. Please note the following results are purely

Figure 18: Single-Phase Stefan Problem: Propagation of the phase-change interface (vertical yellow line) and temperature profile in the liquid melt left of the PCI at different times t . The very coarse mesh with only 10 elements in x -direction is chosen for visualization purposes. The time step size is $\Delta t = 1\text{s}$. The ice right of the interface remains at the melting temperature, $T(x > x_{\text{PCI}}) = T_M$.

numerical tests that function as sanity checks and demonstrate the potential of the simulation tool at hand.

Figure 19: 1D validation: comparison of the simulated interface location $s(t)$ with the analytical solution of the single-phase Stefan problem over time. The simulated propagation is plotted for different mesh resolutions, where the highest resolution corresponds to 80 uniform elements in x -direction on a mesh of total length $\Delta L = 1\text{cm}$

Figure 20: Single phase Stefan problem: absolute error in the numerical prediction of the interface location $\hat{s}(t)$ with respect to the analytical solution $s(t)$. The error is shown for different spatial resolutions ranging from coarse (highest errors) to fine (smallest error) meshes.

Figure 21: Validation: 1D spatial convergence of the predicted interface location $s(t)$ for the single-phase Stefan problem. The plot shows the relative deviation from the analytical solution at a fixed time ($t = 310s$). The time is intentionally chosen not to close to the initial time ($t = 0$) to include a possible summation of errors in the slightly mispredicted numerical location $\hat{s}(t)$ over time. The total length of the domain considered is $\Delta L = 1cm$. The experimental order of convergence (EOC) corresponds to the slope of the linear fit between two consecutive data points in the log-log error plot.

4.2. Test Case: Lid-Driven Melting

In the 1D validation case we neglected the coupling between flow and temperature solution. The *lid-driven melting* case presented in this section serves as a showcase of the coupling strategy discussed in Section 2.1 and sketched in Fig. 3. We furthermore test the ability of our code to handle material properties that are discontinuous across phases.

Fig. 22 shows the test case setup. We consider a square box ($d = 1$) filled with liquid (phase 1, top) and frozen (phase 2, bottom) phase of some material at an initial melting temperature of $T_M = 0$. Note that we will refer to liquid and solid phase also as water and ice respectively, even though the physical parameters used are purely fictional. While the bottom and the laterals $\partial\Omega_{D,o}$ remain static boundaries (no-slip for the velocity, zero-Neumann for the temperature), the upper lid $\partial\Omega_{D,t}$ is moved with a constant velocity $\mathbf{v}_{D,t} = (1, 0)^T$ and kept at a temperature $T_{D,t} > T_M$.

The Prandtl number is defined as the ratio

$$\text{Pr} = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}, \quad (28)$$

between the kinematic viscosity ν and the thermal diffusivity α . We choose a relatively high Prandtl number ($\text{Pr} = 1000$) to emphasize the effects of *convective heat transfer*. Other parameters are detailed in Table 3 and Table 4 of the Appendix.

Starting with both phases at rest ($\mathbf{v}(x, t = 0) = \mathbf{0}$), we solve the weakly-coupled incompressible Navier-Stokes Eqn. (1) and the transient heat Eqn. (5) at each coupling iteration as described in Section 2.1. The governing equations are discretized using stabilized space-time finite elements. While we do not write out the full variational form in this project paper, the proceedings correspond to the descriptions in Section 3 of [32] and in [33]. The uniform structured FEM mesh has a size of 50×50 elements.

The interaction between fluid (top of the box) and ice (at the bottom) is modeled using a discontinuous viscosity. A very high viscosity in the solid phase acts as a penalizer, forcing the velocity \mathbf{v} to be zero at nodes belonging to the solid phase.

The results of the simulation are shown in Fig. 23 at different times t . The color map indicates the temperature (initially $T(\mathbf{x}, t = 0) = T_M$ everywhere) and the small arrows visualize the direction of the flow field. The continuous white line marks the numerically predicted location of the PCI, the interface between liquid and solid phase.

The interaction between flow and temperature field becomes very visible. Since the Prandtl number is high, nearly all heat transfer occurs due to convection. The fluid gets heated at the top lid, and the temperature increase is transported with the motion of the liquid. Since the latent heat is very small, phase change occurs really quickly as soon as temperature gradients are sensed at the interface. Since the strongest gradients

Figure 22: Sketch of the simulation setup for the lid-driven melting test case. In the initial configuration the upper and lower halves of the square box are filled with material of phase 1 and 2 (think water and ice). A constant horizontal velocity $\mathbf{v}_{D,t} = (1, 0)^T$ and a temperature $T_{D,t}$ higher than the melting temperature T_M is prescribed as a Dirichlet boundary on the upper lid ($\partial\Omega_{D,t}$). All other boundaries $\partial\Omega_{D,o}$ are subject to **no-slip** and **zero-Neumann** boundary conditions for velocity and temperature respectively.

occur along the flow streamlines, the interface shape nicely accommodates the vortex forming in the interior of the domain.

At some time $t \gg 0$ all ice has molten and a typical laminar lid-driven flow pattern starts to form. With this simulation we could thus successfully demonstrate the ability to solve coupled simulations and combine flow and phase-change phenomena. For the (stabilized) finite element formulation implemented in [XNS](#) we furthermore find, that the strong discontinuity in the viscosity we used to model the solid phase did not result in numerical instabilities at the interface for the laminar flow considered in this example.

Test Case Parameters: Lid-Driven Melting

domain	Ω	$= [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$
latent heat	h_m	$= 1$
lid velocity	$\mathbf{v}_{D,t}$	$= (1, 0)^T$
lid temperature	$T_{D,t}$	$= 1$
Prandtl number	Pr	$= 1000$
initial temperature	$T_i(\mathbf{x}, t = 0) = T_M$	$= 0$

Table 3: Lid-driven melting: test case parameters. The lid velocity $\mathbf{v}_{D,t}$ and temperature $T_{D,t}$ is the prescribed Dirichlet boundary condition for velocity and temperature on the lid $\partial\Omega_{D,t}$. For a sketch of the domain refer to Fig. 22. Note that we don't name any physical units since we only consider a numerical test case.

Figure 23: Lid-driven melting, simulation results at different times t . A constant velocity and temperature $T_{D,t} > T_M$ is imposed as a Dirichlet condition at the top lid. The interface between the liquid (top) and solid (bottom) phase is marked by the continuous white line. The color map indicates the temperature, the arrows the direction of the flow field. Initially both phases are kept at the melting temperature T_M . Heat transfer occurs mainly through convection and the temperature increase is transported along the streamlines. As the phase change occurs, the interface accommodates the vortex motion of the flow. At $t \gg 0$ all solid material has molten (Fig. 23d). Mesh: 50×50 elements (structured, uniform), time step is $\Delta t = 0.1$

4.3. Test Case: Heated Cylinder

The versatility with respect to the geometry of the computational domain is one major advantage of FEM discretizations. In the previous examples we have however presented cases, which were, due to the particular rectangular shape of their domains, easy to partition by uniform structured meshes. In this last test case we present an example of solidification on a domain with a round cavity, approximated by triangular simplex space-time FEM.

The heated cylinder showcase consists of a circular heated cavity cut out of a box filled with liquid and solid material. This is sketched in Fig. 24. Initially the liquid **phase 1** encases the circular interior boundary $\partial\Omega_{D,i}$ of radius r_Ω . The solid **phase 2** is separated from phase 1 by the circular PCI of initial radius r_{lev} . All material parameters are set to unity, except the thermal conductivities k_i : The liquid phase has a lower conductivity ($k_1 = 0.6$) than the solid ($k_2 = 1$).

The interior and exterior boundaries $\partial\Omega_{D,i}$ and $\partial\Omega_{D,o}$ are both Dirichlet boundaries kept at constant temperatures $T_{D,i} > T_M$ and $T_{D,o} < T_M$ respectively. Due to this condition we expect a physical solution to take on an equilibrium state with a static PCI after some time.

We solve the transient heat Eqn (5) on an unstructured FEM mesh drawn in Fig. 26 of the Appendix.

Fig. 25 shows the mesh and the interface propagation and temperature fields in both phases for the split temperature domains $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,2}$. Each column displays the temperature field inside one of the phases. Initially some of the liquid solidifies. After some time $t \gg 0$ the system reaches an equilibrium state. The PCI roughly preserves its circular shape within the limits of its linear reconstruction within triangular elements, due to the isotropy of the temperature gradients normal to the interface.

Test Case Parameters: Heated Cylinder

cylinder radius	r_Ω	= 0.1
initial PCI radius	r_{lev}	= 0.5
initial temperature	T_i	= $T_m = 0$
pipe temperature	$T_{D,i}$	= 1.0
box temperature	$T_{D,o}$	= -0.5
domain size	d	= 2

Figure 24: Sketch of the simulation setup for the heated cylinder test case. The interior circular boundary $\partial\Omega_{D,i}$ of radius r_Ω is kept at a constant temperature $T_{D,i} > T_M$, the exterior $\partial\Omega_{D,o}$ of the box is cooled at a temperature $T_{D,o} < T_M$. The liquid phase 1 is initially separated from the solid phase 2 by a circular PCI of radius r_{lev} .

Figure 25: Results: Heated Cylinder. The two columns show the two temperature solutions obtained on the domains ghost split by the phase. The PCI is indicated by the left circle. The left column shows the solution obtained in the *solid phase* where $T < T_M$. The right column shows the heated interior *liquid phase*, $T > T_M$. As time progresses liquid partly solidifies. Because the temperature gradients are almost equal in the direction of the interface normal, the PCI preserves its circular shape. After some time $t \gg 0$ the system reaches an equilibrium and the interface does not move anymore. Note that on each split subdomain the nodes belonging to the other phase will remain at the melting temperature $T = T_M$ (cyan color), since they are marked as Dirichlet nodes (see 3.3).

5. Conclusion

In this last chapter we will briefly summarize the findings of this thesis and give a number of suggestions for future work related to our results.

5.1. Summary

In this project paper we

- reviewed the two-phase problem in the context of numerical simulations. We introduced the level-set method and explained why it can be advantageous to use finite elements for the discretization of the governing equation and the level-set equation.
- explained why standard Galerkin [FEM](#) are not suitable for the solution of the two-phase problem without further consideration, due to their inability to capture gradient discontinuities that occur at the interface.
- introduced the concept of the *ghost split* as a remedy to this issue as an alternative to [XFEM](#) with no need for local enrichment of the [FEM](#) basis.
- described how to find the approximate melting velocity using the nodal flux at finite element faces cut by the [PCI](#).
- implemented the coupling of level-set, heat equation and the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations in [XNS](#). A validation against an analytical solution was presented for the simple 1D case of the single-phase Stefan problem. Different showcases on structured and unstructured meshes were presented to test the integrity of the algorithm.

5.2. Outlook

Different aspects of the presented implementation lend themselves to further improvement:

While we have shown the basic functionality of our implementation also for 2D meshes, the simulations conducted do not warrant a full validation. It is therefore necessary to further investigate 2D melting and compare results to other publications or experimental data. This has not been done in this project because many available validation test cases require an additional model for natural convection.

The approximation method for the melting velocity used in this project is based on the pragmatical choice of using the nodal values of the temperature gradient at nodes adjacent to the interface. This decision was made because the nodal gradients were easy to access and because the nodes adjacent to the interface crossings with the mesh

were already known from the level-set reinitialization. This is however not to say that this is the best or most accurate choice to obtain representative fluxes at both sides of the interface.

Finally, we have already briefly touched on extrapolation schemes for the known temperature field onto nodes that are not (yet) part of the considered domain under the current ghost split. Following [9], it would be possible to extend the current implementation with a higher order extrapolation scheme across the interface.

A. Appendix

A.1. Test Case: Additional Information

Phase 1		Phase 2		Global	
k_1	= 1	k_2	= 1	h_m	= 1
μ_1	= 0.5	μ_2	= $10 \cdot 10^3$	$\mathbf{v}_{D,t}$	= $(1, 0)^T$
$c_{p,1}$	= 1000	$c_{p,2}$	= 1	$T_{D,t}$	= 1
ρ_1	= 2	ρ_2	= 1	Pr	= 1000

Table 4: Extended list of parameters used in the lid-driven melting testcase.

Figure 26: Unstructured mesh used for the heated cylinder test case. The initial location of the circular PCI is drawn in yellow.

References

- [1] T. E. Tezduyar, M. Behr, S. Mittal, and J. Liou. A new strategy for finite element computations involving moving boundaries and interfaces - the deforming-spatial-domain/space-time procedure: II. Computation of free-surface flows, two-liquid flows, and flows with drifting cylinders. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 94(3):353–371, 1992.
- [2] A. Tille. Photograph: Eyjafjallajökull outlet glacier.
URL: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Eyjafjallaj%C3%B6kull.jpeg>, 2003.
- [3] G. Hagedorn. Photograph: Molten metal at a furnace outlet.
URL: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Transferring_molten_metal_from_the_furnace_to_the_ladle.jpg, 2007.
- [4] Wikimedia User Fandwisdoywci. Photograph: Noodles in boiling water.
URL: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:HK_Boiling_hot_water_n_noodle_August_2018_IX2_pot_05.jpg, 2018.
- [5] W. M. Plate Jr. Photograph: Metal welding.
URL: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:GMAW.welding.af.ncs.jpg>, 2004.
- [6] E. Maitre. Review of numerical methods for free interfaces. *Les Houches*, 27:31, 2006.
- [7] S. Osher and J. A. Sethian. Fronts propagating with curvature-dependent speed: algorithms based on Hamilton-Jacobi formulations. *Journal of computational physics*, 79(1):12–49, 1988.
- [8] F. Gibou, R. P. Fedkiw, L.-T. Cheng, and M. Kang. A second-order-accurate symmetric discretization of the Poisson equation on irregular domains. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 176(1):205–227, 2002.
- [9] F. Gibou and R. Fedkiw. A fourth order accurate discretization for the Laplace and heat equations on arbitrary domains, with applications to the Stefan problem. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 202(2):577–601, 2005.
- [10] S. Chen, B. Merriman, S. Osher, and P. Smereka. A simple level set method for solving Stefan problems. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 135(1):8–29, 1997.
- [11] S. Groß, V. Reichelt, and A. Reusken. A finite element based level set method for two-phase incompressible flows. *Computing and visualization in science*, 9(4):239–257, 2006.

-
- [12] S. Valance, R. de Borst, J. Réthoré, and M. Coret. *A Finite Element Method for Level Sets*, pages 95–106. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 2009.
- [13] F. Gibou, L. Chen, D. Nguyen, and S. Banerjee. A level set based sharp interface method for the multiphase incompressible Navier–Stokes equations with phase change. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 222(2):536–555, 2007.
- [14] L. Pauli. *Stabilized Finite Element Methods for Computational Design of Blood-Handling Devices*. Verlag Dr. Hut, 2016.
- [15] H. Hu and S. A. Argyropoulos. Mathematical modelling of solidification and melting: a review. *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, 4(4):371, 1996.
- [16] D. Juric and G. Tryggvason. Computations of boiling flows. *International journal of multiphase flow*, 24(3):387–410, 1998.
- [17] N. D. Katopodes. Chapter 12 - Volume of Fluid Method". In N. D. Katopodes, editor, *Free-Surface Flow*, pages 766 – 802. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2019.
- [18] S. WJ. Welch and J. Wilson. A volume of fluid based method for fluid flows with phase change. *Journal of computational physics*, 160(2):662–682, 2000.
- [19] N. D. Katopodes. Chapter 13 - Level Set Method. In N. D. Katopodes, editor, *Free-Surface Flow*, pages 804 – 828. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2019.
- [20] CR. Swaminathan and V. R. Voller. A general enthalpy method for modeling solidification processes. *Metallurgical transactions B*, 23(5):651–664, 1992.
- [21] M. Bernauer. Motion Planning for the Two-Phase Stefan Problem in Level Set Formulation. 2010.
- [22] R. Kimmel and J. A. Sethian. Computing geodesic paths on manifolds. *Proceedings of the national academy of Sciences*, 95(15):8431–8435, 1998.
- [23] J. Stefan. Über die Theorie der Eisbildung, insbesondere über die Eisbildung im Polarmeere. *Annalen der Physik*, 278(2):269–286, 1891.
- [24] K. Schüller. Development of a finite element model to describe the dynamic behaviour of the maneuverable ice exploration probe IceMole. Master’s thesis, FH Aachen University of Applied Sciences, 2015.
- [25] J. Donea and A. Huerta. *Finite element methods for flow problems*. John Wiley & Sons, 2003.
- [26] L. Pauli and M. Behr. On stabilized space-time fem for anisotropic meshes: Incompressible navier–stokes equations and applications to blood flow in medical devices. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids*, 85(3):189–209, 2017.

-
- [27] J. E. Dolbow. An extended finite element method with discontinuous enrichment for applied mechanics. 2000.
- [28] J. Chessa, P. Smolinski, and T. Belytschko. The extended finite element method (XFEM) for solidification problems. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 53(8):1959–1977, 2002.
- [29] M. Bernauer. Motion Planning for the Two-Phase Stefan Problem in Level Set Formulation. 2010.
- [30] T. D. Aslam. A partial differential equation approach to multidimensional extrapolation. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 193(1):349–355, 2004.
- [31] J. Kowalski. Summary Script: Advanced Mathematical Modeling in Applied Geoscience. RWTH Aachen University, 2019.
- [32] F. Key, L. Pauli, and S. Elgeti. The Virtual Ring Shear-Slip Mesh Update Method. *Computers & Fluids*, 172:352 – 361, 2018.
- [33] V. Karyofylli, M. Behr, M. Schmitz, and C. Hopmann. Novel discretization methods for improved simulation precision in injection molding: Neue Diskretisierungsmethoden für gesteigerte Simulationsqualität im Spritzgießen. *Materialwissenschaft und Werkstofftechnik*, 48(12):1264–1269, 2017.